

Rural water point mapping with/in OSM: implications of recent research in Malawi

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This paper provides a brief review of the state of water point mapping associated with and beyond OSM, with a focus on rural Malawi in south-eastern Africa. The review is offered to stimulate exchange with other researchers who are similarly concerned to address ways to leverage OpenStreetMap (OSM) to enhance management and development of rural water services. It stems from recent research conducted by the author on drinking water quality in southern Malawi, which has also included a new collaboration with a community-based organisation (CBO) with its own record of supporting local community water management developed over several years. As well as drawing on the author's own experiences working with this CBO the review also considers papers from other recent Malawi-focussed research projects plus reflections of a separate sub-Saharan water development specialist.

As in many Least Developed Country contexts the water service infrastructure across rural Malawi is generally at a basic-only level. Typically 'water points' refers to communal infrastructure such as pumped boreholes, protected springs, or gravity flow schemes. In rural Malawi such supply points (especially hand-pumped boreholes) exist in their tens of thousands, many created with funding from the charitable endeavours of non-governmental organisations. Otherwise, infrastructure investment (either public or private) remains limited, while widespread poverty affects many users' ability to pay for water services.

As well as being a key lifeline for rural communities, water points are relatively prominent features, located in the open air within or near rural settlements. However, despite such characteristics, water points in rural Malawi are presently not well mapped in OSM, with a search of the OSM database (for Malawi as a whole) finding a minute fraction of nodes - around just 200 - associated with appropriate tags ('amenity=drinking water'; 'man_made=water_well'). Moreover, this situation is despite several efforts over the last decade to increase OSM data creation within and about Malawi, most notably via Humanitarian OpenStreetMap, Missing Maps and the Youth Mappers initiative.

However, the motivation for this paper lies less with the goal of increasing numbers of water points within OSM than with considering how knowledge of and engagements with OSM may contribute to improved compilation, sharing and use of water point data more broadly. A rather similar perspective to this has been adopted in other recent work,

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specifically by a research consortium led by the 510 initiative of The Netherlands Red Cross [1]. This consortium approached the aforementioned challenges in the context of exploring combinations of 'Big' and 'Small' Data to enhance reporting on Target 6.1 of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): namely, to achieve, by 2030, 'universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all'. In the consortium's study, 'big' data included those extractable from earth observation imagery, and 'small' data include geo-located water point datasets created by various water-sector organisations as part of their own regular activities (further information and links to the latter are available at [2]). The study entailed overlaying these datasets together, to identify and reduce locational inconsistencies among the water point datasets, and to explore enriching them with additional attribute data. Building outlines created in OSM were also included in the overlay process, both to assist the checking of water point locations and to provide a basis for making crude estimates of water demand. Water points were visually detected from custom-flown high-resolution drone imagery, supporting assessment of locational inconsistencies across the other existing datasets. In consequence, the workflow developed including the drone imagery was deemed cost-effective over limited size study areas.

The existing geo-located water point datasets just mentioned contain considerably larger numbers of water points than OSM, albeit varying in their spatial coverage, content, quality and currency. These variations reflect the multiplicity of stakeholders working in Malawi's rural water supply sector, as well as limits of official data and in terms of data coordination, data sharing and wider data literacy. The same 501-led consortium also conducted a 'data ecosystem'-based assessment of this situation, to assess further the prospects for enhanced SDG monitoring [3]. For that assessment the water point datasets (including OSM) were scored according to various standardised data supply characteristics. While the OSM dataset had smaller numbers of water points than others, it nonetheless scored higher for some characteristics, including for data reliability and accuracy, reflecting the processes within OSM whereby experienced users conduct validation checks of new data. However, the OSM data were also more limited in the range of water point attributes they included.

Broadly contemporaneous to these studies, the Scottish Government Climate Justice Fund Water Futures Programme, working in partnership with Government of Malawi, has undertaken to compile a major new rural water supplies asset register, covering all of Malawi [4]. Hosted on a third-party water data management platform (mWater - not connected with OSM), this register is reported to have included field inspections of all water supply points, so as to enable thorough assessment of supply sustainability. The creation of this new register suggests that data-based policy development in respect of water services is being taken seriously. Furthermore, it could also be construed as an initial step away from current community-based water management models, instead towards a more centralised and professionalised approach to water service delivery and management. Such a community-professional transition appears all the more desirable given that, at any given time, a high proportion, almost half, of all survey water supply points are identified as not functioning to standard, suggesting that many communities are incapable of effective management [4]. However, a question is whether such numbers reflect inherent failings of rural water-using communities themselves, or instead whether they reflect inadequacies in support and capacity development provided by organisations favouring community-based management [5].

The author's partnership with the CBO suggests community-based water management can actually be effective, provided sufficient planning, monitoring and resourcing are available to communities and supporting organisations. The CBO's own programme encompasses several elements: comprehensive baseline surveys of water points; targeted training for local water user communities; routine monitoring and refresher training; and programmes for sourcing and quality control of replacement pump parts [6,7]. In addition, many of the baseline and monitoring data collected are entered onto the CBO's own public-facing water point data sharing platform, Madzi Alipo (<https://www.madzialipoapp.org>), which is also integrated with a custom designed mobile data collection app. Through its independence from government, and because of its reputation undertaking other community development projects, the CBO is well-placed to develop trusted relationships with local community water committees. Nonetheless, our experience working with them reveals several challenges with data handling, management and integration which risk undermining the value of community engagement and data collection efforts.

Where does this leave us? There are a number of implications and opportunities to discuss further. These include, first, the possibilities for using higher resolution imagery, in conjunction with algorithmic methods, for more automated and scaled-up rural water point mapping, and for shortening data update cycles. Second, with regard to improving data coordination, consistency and sharing, encompassing both locational data and data on the functional status and other attributes of water points (e.g., water quality). Third, considering also the scope to improve the data management and analysis capacity of CBOs, and likewise, the capacity and involvement of local communities in data collection and monitoring activities.

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